

MISUSE OF PENILE PERFORMANCE ENHANCERS: AWARENESS GAPS AND RISK OF PRIAPISM—A PILOT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The use of penile performance enhancers has become increasingly common, particularly among young individuals, yet concerns remain about how well users understand the associated risks. This pilot study explored patterns of use, awareness gaps, and perceptions related to priapism among residents of Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey was conducted using a structured, pretested questionnaire administered to 121 respondents, most of whom were young, single, and tertiary-educated. While awareness of penile performance enhancers was high (82.6%), knowledge of priapism was notably lower (50.8%). Although a majority recognised that misuse could lead to complications, uncertainty persisted, especially regarding the safety of herbal products. Many respondents perceived unsupervised use as risky, yet also believed that individuals rarely seek medical advice before use. Formal education on the risks of misuse was limited, but the need for more information was widely expressed. Importantly, respondents anticipated both medical and traditional responses to complications, suggesting a pattern of pluralistic help-seeking that may delay access to appropriate care. Prior exposure to health education was associated with better awareness of risks. These findings suggest a disconnect between awareness and understanding, underscoring the need for targeted, context-sensitive health education to promote safer practices and timely care-seeking behaviour.

Keywords: Penile performance enhancers, Priapism, Substance misuse, Risk awareness, Health-seeking behaviour, Young adults

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INTRODUCTION

Priapism is described as the sustained erection of the penis and occurs in the absence of sexual stimulation. It is considered to be a medical emergency that requires urgent management (Moodley *et al.*, 2024; Naman *et al.*, 2024). Although rare, priapism may lead to complications that cause harm if management is not sought immediately (Moodley *et al.*, 2024; Yarak *et al.*, 2024; Leong *et al.*, 2025). Drug induced priapism is increasingly reported compared to the traditional causes relating to hematological disorders (Moodley *et al.*, 2024; Schifano *et al.*, 2024; Abbasi *et al.*, 2024).

Over the past decade, PDE5 inhibitors such as sildenafil and tadalafil have become more available to purchase outside of clinical settings (Schifano *et al.*, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2024). While these drugs are generally used to treat erectile dysfunction when prescribed by medical professional, young males reportedly misuse them recreationally with or without the diagnosis of sexual dysfunction (Wdowiak *et al.*, 2024; Pantazis *et al.*, 2024). Herbal aphrodisiacs and other sexual enhancement products are also regularly used and often contain hidden pharmacologically active ingredients which users can be unintentionally exposed to (Mugiyanto *et al.*, 2025; Wang *et al.*, 2026).

While many people who use performance enhancers may not experience problems, there are adverse consequences that have been associated with their use. These consequences can include priapism and other urological issues (Abbasi *et al.*, 2024; Schifano *et al.*, 2024; Trifu *et al.*, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Although this may be rare, misuse of these substances can lead to serious side effects if the use is prolonged or unsupervised by a medical professional (Moodley *et al.*, 2024; Ganapathy *et al.*, 2021). In addition, using these substances can alter one's sexual behaviour, leading them to engage in risk-taking activities that could further amplify chances of experiencing an adverse outcome (Soltaninejad *et al.*, 2024; Rao *et al.*, 2024).

Individuals may be aware of the reasons for using aphrodisiacs, but their lack of understanding of the associated risks remains limited, which is a cause for concern. This aligns with the findings by Fatade *et al.* (2024), who reported that among male university students in Southwest Nigeria, only 38.9% of those who had heard of or used aphrodisiacs, recognised their potential health risks.

When an individual experiences an adverse consequence that they associate with the use of a performance enhancer, their response to the symptoms may be uncertain or confused. In many communities where alternative forms of care are prevalent, people may draw on a combination of formal and informal healthcare when they become ill (Meyer-Weitz *et al.*, 2000; Adejumo *et al.*, 2016). Such decisions are often shaped by cultural beliefs and an individual's understanding of their condition. In the case of priapism, which is a urological emergency, delays in seeking appropriate treatment can lead to serious complications (Moodley *et al.*, 2024; Yarak *et al.*, 2024; Leong *et al.*, 2025).

Previous studies have examined the adverse effects associated with drug use as well as patterns of substance use (Abbasi *et al.*, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2024; Soltaninejad *et al.*, 2024). However, fewer studies have explored how these elements interact, particularly in relation to how individuals respond to complications arising from performance enhancer use. While drugs have been shown to cause priapism and other side effects, there remains limited understanding of how users of these substances would react if such adverse effects occur.

The present pilot study aims to assess knowledge of penile performance enhancer use among residents of Makurdi in Benue State, Nigeria. It focuses on patterns of use, level of awareness, and associated risks, while also exploring how individuals may respond to adverse outcomes such as priapism.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: This study was designed as a pilot cross-sectional investigation aimed at gaining an initial understanding of how young people engage with penile performance enhancers, what they know about the associated risks, and how they respond when complications occur. Given the limited existing data in this area, a pilot approach was considered appropriate to generate preliminary insights that could inform future, larger studies. The sample size of 121 participants was considered adequate for this pilot study to generate preliminary insights and guide the design of future, more representative studies.

Inclusion Criteria: Participants were eligible if they were youths or young adults within the age of 18 years and above and had either used, or were at least aware of, penile performance enhancers. This included both pharmaceutical agents, such as sildenafil or tadalafil, and herbal or traditional products. By including both users and non-users, the study was able to capture a broader picture of awareness, perception, and behaviour, consistent with previous work in similar populations (Fatade *et al.*, 2024; Wdowiak *et al.*, 2024).

Sampling Method: A convenience sampling approach was used, largely because of the exploratory nature of the study and the sensitivity of the subject matter. In adopting this approach, consideration was given to the fact that discussions around sexual health and performance may influence individuals' willingness to participate. Recruiting participants from accessible groups therefore provided a practical way of gathering data while ensuring that respondents felt comfortable enough to engage. However, this approach may limit the representativeness of the sample and, consequently, the generalizability of the findings.

Ethical Considerations: This study was conducted as an anonymous questionnaire-based survey with minimal risk to participants. Participation was entirely voluntary, and

informed consent was obtained from all respondents before data collection. No personally identifiable information was collected and all responses were handled with strict confidentiality. As this was an exploratory pilot study, institutional ethical approval was not obtained. Nevertheless, the study was carried out in line with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013). Participants were clearly informed about the purpose of the study, assured that their responses would remain confidential, and given the freedom to participate without any pressure or fear of judgement.

Data Collection: Data were obtained by a structured 27-item questionnaire covering socio-demographics, awareness and use of penile performance enhancers (PPEs), risk knowledge (including priapism), precautions and health-seeking behaviour. The instrument was pre-tested for clarity, and sections addressing awareness and perception were informed by previous studies on aphrodisiac use (Fatade *et al.*, 2024). Items included yes/no, multiple-choice and ordinal response formats. A composite awareness score (0–5) was derived from 5 items: awareness of priapism, awareness of PPEs, recognition of prolonged erection or complications, knowledge that misuse can cause priapism, and prior exposure to risk education. Each correct or affirmative response contributed one point, with higher scores indicating greater awareness and enabling subgroup comparisons.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 27 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics summarized participant characteristics and key study variables. Categorical data were presented as frequencies and percentages. Continuous variables were summarized using means, standard deviations, medians, and interquartile ranges as needed. Inferential analyses explored associations between variables. Fisher’s exact test was used for comparisons between categorical variables due to small subgroup sizes. The Mann-Whitney U test was applied for comparisons of non-normally distributed continuous variables between groups. Paired ordinal responses were analyzed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank

test. Odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals were calculated for selected associations. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Given the exploratory nature of this pilot study and the potential for small subgroup sizes, effect estimates and confidence intervals will be interpreted with appropriate caution.

RESULTS

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of survey respondents. Respondents were young and otherwise socio-demographically homogenous. The majority of respondents were aged 18–24 years (104/121, 86.0%), single (119/121, 98.3%), tertiary educated (115/121, 95.0%) and students (116/121, 95.9%). Standardization of free-text location responses revealed that 115/119 respondents with valid location data (96.6%) lived in Benue State or included a Makurdi-area place in their free-text location response.

Awareness of Priapism and Penile Performance Enhancers

Asking whether they had heard of priapism showed awareness was balanced: 60/119 valid respondents (50.4%) reported being aware of priapism vs. 59 (49.6%) who had not. Awareness of penile performance enhancers was substantially higher with 99/120 (82.5%) reporting prior awareness of medications or supplements used as penile performance enhancers.

Prescription drugs was the enhancer category most frequently mentioned (36/118, 30.5%), followed by other mixtures/concoctions (33/118, 28.0%) and herbs (26/118, 22.0%). Ninety-one respondents (91/121, 75.8%) reported being aware that abuse of penile performance enhancers can lead to serious complications including priapism, and 77 (77/120, 64.2%) had heard of prolonged erections or other complications resulting from the use of performance enhancers.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents (n = 121)

Characteristic	Category	n	Valid %
Age	18-24	104	86.0
	25-31	16	13.2
	32 and above	1	0.8
Gender	Male	61	50.4
	Female	60	49.6
Marital Status	Single	119	98.3
	Married	2	1.7
Educational Level	Tertiary	115	95.0
	Secondary	6	5.0
Occupation	Student	116	95.9
	None/Unemployed	4	3.3
	Civil Servant	1	0.8
Location group	Benue	115	96.6
	Kogi	1	0.8
	Nasarawa	1	0.8
	FCT	1	0.8
	Other/unclear	1	0.8

Perceived Importance, Risk, and Barriers to Care-Seeking

Overall, perceived psychosocial importance and perceived risk regarding erectile dysfunction medications were high. Over half of respondents considered penile performance to be very important to self-image or confidence (67/117, 57.3%). Additionally, 79 of 120 respondents (65.8%) rated unsupervised use of enhancers as very risky and another 28 respondents (23.3%) considered it moderately risky. Most respondents also perceived embarrassment about using erectile dysfunction medications to be a barrier to seeking professional care. When asked if people feel embarrassed to seek medical advice before using such products, 88 of 120 respondents answered “yes,” while 20 respondents (16.7%) answered “somewhat”.

Attitudes about Safety and Community Use

Beliefs about safety were somewhat ambivalent. While 65 of 121 respondents valid percent (53.7%) disagreed with the statement “Herbal or natural male enhancement products are totally safe”, 39 (32.2%) were unsure and 17 (14.0%) agreed.

The majority of respondents believed that penile performance enhancers are commonly used in their community (108/120, 90.0%). Use was considered occasional by 74 of 119 respondents (62.2%) and frequent by 34 (28.6%). Instructions are followed or a healthcare provider is consulted rarely according to 60 of 120 respondents (50.0%) and never according to 9 (7.5%), while only 3 respondents (2.5%) felt users always follow directions or speak with a healthcare provider.

Risk Education/Information Received

Risk education received was sparse. Thirty-four of 119 respondents (28.6%) reported receiving risk education regarding misuse, while 85 respondents (71.4%) did not receive formal risk education. Although misuse education was limited among respondents, desire for health information was prevalent. Of the 116 valid respondents, 107 (92.2%) indicated needing more information regarding safe use and associated risks. Healthcare providers were seen as the most desirable place to obtain information (108 respondents, 90.8% valid, 88.5% overall). Community programs/workshops were a distant second place to obtain information (23 respondents, 19.3%), followed by internet/social media (13 respondents, 10.9%), then friends/peers (7 respondents, 5.9%)

Table 2: Awareness, prior exposure, education, and information needs

Awareness/knowledge item	Response	n	Valid %
Heard of priapism	Yes	60	50.4
	No	59	49.6
Heard of penile performance enhancers	Yes	99	82.5
	No	21	17.5
Most recognized enhancer type	Prescription Drugs	36	30.5
	Other mixtures and concoctions	33	28.0
	Herbs	26	22.0
	Self-procured drugs	23	19.5
Aware misuse can cause priapism	Yes	91	75.8
	No	29	24.2
Heard of prolonged erections/other complications	Yes	76	63.9
	No	30	25.2
	Not sure	13	10.9
Received education about misuse risks	No	85	71.4
	Yes	34	28.6
Need more information	Yes	107	92.2
	No	9	7.8

Anticipated Actions if an Adverse Event Occurs

When respondents were asked what actions someone would take if they experienced prolonged erection after using enhancer, 83 of 117 respondents who provided valid responses (70.9%) answered that the person would seek immediate care from medical professionals either "likely" or "very likely". However, 67 of 117 respondents (57.3%) answered that they would seek help from spiritual healers or use traditional medicines either "likely" or "very likely". On paired ordinal analysis, participants were significantly more likely to seek immediate medical care than spiritual or traditional help (Wilcoxon signed-rank $p = 0.002$). However, because these responses are not mutually exclusive and participants could answer both, this may also reflect pluralistic help seeking behaviour.

Composite Awareness Score and Group Differences

The median composite awareness score was 3.0 out of 5 points (mean 2.98 ± 1.50 , interquartile range 2.0–4.0). Awareness scores did not differ significantly between male and female respondents (Mann–Whitney $U p = 0.356$), nor between respondents aged 18–24 years and those ≥ 25 years old ($p = 0.563$). Note that interpretation of the age-related finding is limited by the small number of respondents ≥ 25 years old ($n = 18$).

Factors Associated with Awareness and Behaviour

Results of exploratory subgroup analyses consistently demonstrated a positive association between any prior exposure to related information and awareness of priapism as a potential complication of misuse. Individuals who reported previously receiving education about risks associated with enhancer misuse were significantly more likely to correctly identify misuse as a potential cause of priapism compared to individuals who did not report previous education about misuse (97.1% vs 67.9%, $p < 0.001$).

Respondents who reported having heard of priapism were more likely to know that enhancer misuse can cause priapism (96.7% vs 55.9%, $p < 0.001$), as were respondents who reported knowing what penile performance enhancers are (82.8% vs 47.6%, $p = 0.001$).

Male respondents were significantly more likely than females to report that they would or might informally recommend a sexual enhancer product to someone without consulting a doctor first (15/61 [24.6%] vs 0/58 [0%], $p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Perceptions, attitudes, and expected help-seeking

Perception/attitude item	Response	n	Valid %
Importance to self-image/confidence	Very Important	67	57.3
	Somewhat Important	38	32.5
	Not Important	12	10.3
Perceived risk without medical supervision	Very risky	79	65.8
	Moderately risky	28	23.3
	I do not know	13	10.8
Perceived embarrassment/hesitation to seek care	Yes	88	73.3
	Somewhat	20	16.7
	Not at all	12	10.0
Belief that herbal/natural enhancers are safe	No	65	53.7
	Not Sure	39	32.2
	Yes	17	14.0
Belief that people use enhancers	Yes	108	90.0
	Maybe	10	8.3
	No	2	1.7
Perceived frequency of use	Occasionally	74	62.2
	Frequently	34	28.6
	Rarely	9	7.6
	Never	2	1.7
Perceived adherence/consultation before use	Rarely	60	50.0
	Yes sometimes	48	40.0
	Never	9	7.5
	Yes always	3	2.5
Likelihood of seeking immediate medical care	Very likely	43	36.8
	Likely	40	34.2
	Unlikely	29	24.8
	Very unlikely	5	4.3
Likelihood of seeking spiritual/traditional help	Likely	45	38.5
	Unlikely	37	31.6
	Very likely	22	18.8
	Very unlikely	13	11.1
Can users identify safe vs unsafe enhancers	Maybe	48	40.3
	No	45	37.8
	Yes	26	21.8
Would recommend without medical advice	No	105	87.5
	Yes	8	6.7
	Maybe	7	5.8
Can serve a medical purpose	Yes	76	63.3
	Maybe	31	25.8
	No	13	10.8

Table 4: Trusted information sources for penile performance enhancers and sexual health.

Trusted source	Selected, n	% of respondents with valid responses
Healthcare providers	108	90.8
Community programs or workshops	23	19.3
Internet or social media	13	10.9
Friends or peers	7	5.9

Multiple responses were allowed; percentages therefore do not sum to 100%.

Table 5: Selected exploratory inferential findings

Comparison	Outcome	Observed proportions	Odds ratio (95% CI)	P value
Received education vs no education	Aware misuse can cause priapism	33/34 (97.1%) vs 57/84 (67.9%)	15.63 (2.03 to 120.40)	<0.001
Heard of priapism vs not heard	Aware misuse can cause priapism	58/60 (96.7%) vs 33/59 (55.9%)	22.85 (5.10 to 102.44)	<0.001
Heard of enhancers vs not heard	Aware misuse can cause priapism	82/99 (82.8%) vs 10/21 (47.6%)	5.31 (1.95 to 14.47)	0.001
Male vs female respondents	Would recommend without medical advice (yes/maybe)	15/61 (24.6%) vs 0/58 (0.0%)	39.00 (2.27 to 669.13)	<0.001

All p values are from Fisher’s test. Odds ratios are shown with 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 1: Key awareness, education, and information-need indicators. Percentages are valid percentages based on non-missing responses

Figure 2: Distribution of selected perceptions and attitudes. Each bar sums to 100% of valid responses for that item

Figure 3: Trusted information sources. Multiple responses were permitted

Figure 4: Expected responses to prolonged erection after enhancer use

The results indicate that knowledge of PPEs is common among participants, whereas knowledge of priapism and education about misuse appears less widespread. Negative beliefs about using PPEs unsupervised and high levels of trust in health care professionals suggest that interventions addressing persistent uncertainty about safety of herbal medicine, perceived poor adherence with medical advice, and traditional/spiritualistic help-seeking behaviors may be beneficial.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study point to a clear gap between awareness of penile performance enhancers and a deeper understanding of their associated risks. While many respondents were familiar with these substances, fewer were aware of priapism as a potential complication. This suggests that familiarity does not necessarily translate into meaningful risk awareness. Similar patterns have been reported in previous studies, where sildenafil and related agents were used without a clear appreciation of their adverse effects, particularly among younger populations (Wdowiak *et al.*, 2024; Abbasi *et al.*, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2024).

The high level of awareness observed in this study likely reflects the increasing accessibility of these substances. Phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitors, in particular, are known to be used outside clinical settings, including for recreational purposes among young men without diagnosed erectile dysfunction (Wdowiak *et al.*, 2024; Pantazis *et al.*, 2024). Evidence from pharmacovigilance studies further indicates that these medications are associated with adverse outcomes such as priapism (Abbasi *et al.*, 2024; Schifano *et al.*, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2024; Trifu *et al.*, 2024; Lui *et al.*, 2023). Taken together, these findings reinforce the concern that increased access, in the absence of adequate guidance, may expose users to avoidable risks. In this context, drug-induced priapism is increasingly recognised as an important clinical issue (Moodley *et al.*, 2024; Yarak *et al.*, 2024).

The findings also draw attention to the role of herbal and traditional aphrodisiacs. Although widely recognised within the study population, their safety is not always well understood. Some of these products may contain undeclared pharmacologically active substances, which raises concerns about unintentional exposure to potent agents, particularly when used without medical supervision

(Mugiyanto *et al.*, 2025; Wang *et al.*, 2026). This highlights an additional layer of risk that may not be immediately apparent to users and underscores the need for greater scrutiny and regulation of such products (Vishwakarma *et al.*, 2024).

Behavioural and psychosocial factors also appear to play an important role in the use of penile performance enhancers. The importance placed on sexual performance by many respondents suggests that motivations for use may extend beyond clinical need. This aligns with existing literature linking substance use to sexual behaviour and risk-taking, particularly among young adults (Soltaninejad *et al.*, 2024; Rao *et al.*, 2024). In such contexts, perceived benefits may outweigh concerns about potential harm, which may partly explain the continued use of these substances despite awareness of associated risks.

Despite recognising the potential dangers of unsupervised use, respondents also perceived that safe practices—such as seeking medical advice—are not consistently followed. This reflects a broader pattern observed in substance use research, where awareness alone may not necessarily translate into behaviour change among young people (Soltaninejad *et al.*, 2024; Astolfi *et al.*, 2021). The findings therefore point to a gap not only in knowledge, but also in how that knowledge is applied in practice.

The expectation that individuals may seek both medical and traditional or spiritual care in response to complications highlights the influence of context on health-seeking behaviour. Rather than following a single pathway, individuals may draw on multiple sources of care, reflecting the role of cultural beliefs in shaping how illness is understood and managed (Meyer-Weitz *et al.*, 2000; Adejumo *et al.*, 2016). In the case of priapism, where timely medical intervention is critical, such pluralistic approaches may contribute to delays and poorer outcomes (Moodley *et al.*, 2024; Yarak *et al.*, 2024; Leong *et al.*, 2025).

The strong association between prior exposure to health information and improved awareness observed in this study further underscores the importance of education. Previous work has shown that awareness and perception of aphrodisiac use are shaped by exposure to relevant health information (Fatade *et al.*, 2024). This suggests that targeted, context-sensitive educational interventions may be

effective in improving understanding and promoting safer practices.

Finally, the observed gender differences in recommendation behaviour may reflect broader patterns in risk-related practices. Male respondents were more likely to indicate that they might recommend these substances without medical advice, which may be linked to differences in attitudes toward risk and health behaviour (Soltaninejad *et al.*, 2024; Rao *et al.*, 2024). Addressing such differences may require more tailored approaches in future public health interventions.

Overall, the findings of this study suggest that the use of penile performance enhancers is shaped by a complex interplay of awareness, behavioural influences, and contextual factors. Addressing these elements in a coordinated and contextually relevant manner may be the key to reducing the risks associated with their use and improving health outcomes.

Conclusion

Our study offers a glimpse into a growing but often overlooked public health concern—the indiscriminate use of penile performance enhancers among young individuals in Makurdi. What stands out is not just how widespread awareness of these substances has become, but how uneven that awareness is when it comes to understanding their potential risks, particularly priapism. Many respondents appeared to recognise that unsupervised use could be harmful, yet this awareness did not consistently translate into cautious or informed behaviour.

There is also a striking interplay between knowledge, perception, and cultural context. While respondents expressed trust in healthcare professionals and acknowledged the risks involved, uncertainty around the safety of herbal products and the continued inclination toward traditional or spiritual remedies suggest that decision-making in this area is far from straightforward. Importantly, those who had been previously exposed to relevant health information demonstrated better awareness, reinforcing the idea that education can make a meaningful difference.

Taken together, these findings point to a situation where exposure to penile performance enhancers is high, but understanding and safe practices have not kept pace.

Addressing this imbalance is essential if preventable complications such as priapism are to be reduced.

Recommendations

The findings of this study suggest a clear need for more intentional and context-sensitive health education efforts, particularly among young people, focusing not only on the risks associated with penile performance enhancers but also on the importance of early recognition of complications such as priapism and timely medical care. Given the predominantly student population, integrating sexual health education into school and university programs could provide a practical entry point for improving awareness and shaping safer behaviours. At the community level, awareness campaigns should aim to address persistent misconceptions, especially the belief that herbal or “natural” enhancers are inherently safe, while also encouraging more open and informed conversations about sexual health. Efforts to strengthen engagement with healthcare services are equally important, particularly in reducing the stigma or embarrassment that may delay care-seeking. In parallel, there is a need for closer regulation and monitoring of both pharmaceutical and herbal sexual enhancement products to reduce the risks associated with misuse and adulteration. Finally, this pilot study highlights the importance of further research, and larger, more diverse studies are needed particularly in the northern part of Nigeria where anecdotal and emerging evidence suggest that the use of sex enhancers are rampant, to better understand how these patterns vary across different populations and to inform more targeted interventions.

Limitations

While this study provides useful preliminary insights, its findings should be interpreted with some caution. The study population was largely composed of young, tertiary-educated students from a single geographic area, which means the results may not fully reflect the experiences or behaviours of other groups, particularly older individuals or those in different socio-cultural settings. The use of convenience sampling also means that the participants may not be entirely representative of the wider population, as those who chose to participate could differ in important ways from those who did not.

In addition, the study relied on self-reported data, which introduces the possibility of recall bias and social desirability bias, especially given the sensitive nature of the subject. Some of the findings, particularly those relating to expected responses to complications, reflect perceptions rather than actual behaviours, and may therefore not accurately predict real-world actions. The cross-sectional design further limits the ability to draw causal inferences, as the relationships observed represent associations at a single point in time. Finally, as a pilot study, the results are exploratory and intended to guide future research rather than provide definitive conclusions.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

All authors contributed to the study design, data collection and analysis, manuscript drafting, and critical revisions, and approved the final version of the manuscript.

